

Effect of organic nutrient management on growth and yield of cauliflower (*Brassica oleraceae* L. var. *botrytis*)

Udaya Prakash Chongbang¹, Karun Adhikari^{2*}, Ashis Rai²
and Kailash Shrestha²

¹Nepal Polytechnic Institute, Chitwan, Nepal

²Himalayan College of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, Kirtipur, Nepal

*Corresponding Author: karunadhikary45@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

An experiment was carried out in Dawan, Bhojpur to evaluate the efficacy of different organic sources of nutrients on growth and yield of cauliflower (*Brassica oleraceae* L. var. *botrytis*) from February 2020 to May 2020. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and four different organic and conventional sourcenutrientsrient viz. Farm Yard Manure, Poultry manure, Mustard oil cake, Vermicompost, and control were taken as treatments and replicated 4 times. Results indicated that there was a significant difference in growth regarding plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf length, canopy area, curd weight ,and biomass weight between the different organic sources of the nutrient. Maximum plant height (41.35cm), maximum number of leaves per plant (17.57), maximum leaf length (35.05cm), highest canopy area (28.69), maximum curd weight (728.4g) was observed in treatment with Farm Yard Manure. On the other hand, Maximum biomass weight was observed in Vermicompost (1285gm). Minimum growth and yield were observed in control i.e. plant height (30.06cm), number of leaves (13.20), leaf length (25.67cm), canopy area (20.35), curd weight (328.7g) and biomass weight (686g). Although highest growth on most parameters was observed in FYM, all the other 3 treatments showed significant difference in growth and yield with regards to control. This finding indicated the effectivity of conventional and organic nutrient management, particularly FYM over control suggesting use of these nutrient sources as alternative to chemical fertilizers.

Keywords: Organic, Nutrients, Cauliflower, Fertilizers, Canopy area

INTRODUCTION

Cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L. var *botrytis*), a crucifer, is one of the several vegetables in the genus *Brassica*, which shares its family, Brassicaceae with others cole crop like broccoli, Brussels sprouts, cabbage, collard greens and kale.

This vegetable constitutes about 13% of the total area under vegetable cultivation in Nepal which translates roughly to 32,98,816 ha. Furthermore, among vegetables, Cauliflower contributes highest in terms of production i.e. 5,50,004.8 tons annually (MoAD, 2016). Regardless, among green vegetables, Nepal imports large amount of cauliflower (Dhakal, 2021).

Productivity of a crop, beside other factors, depends largely on the soil property. Chemical fertilizer are popular because of their quick access and higher nutrient use efficiency, and has no doubt been an influential factor in ramping up production to meet global demands. But this comes at a cost, prolonged use of synthetic fertilizers result in reduction of organic carbon and organic matter, nutrient imbalance, deficiency of secondary macronutrients and micronutrients (Hossain *et al.*, 2022). The increase in unbalanced and rampant use of chemical fertilizers, has severe impact on the soil property, environment health and finances and can thereby result in negative effects such as aggravated acidification and alkalization, leaching, pollution of water resources, destruction of microorganisms in soil and useful insects, crop susceptibility to disease attack, reduction in soil fertility, nutrient imbalance, compaction of soil thus causing irreparable damage to the overall system (Hossain *et al.*, 2021). In Nepal, more than 90% of the commercial farmers use pesticides and commercial fertilizers (Joshi and Piya, 2021) and rampant overuse of chemical fertilizers and pesticides degrades soil and water (Dahal and Manandhar, 2021).

Organic manure on the other hand has been conventionally used for centuries in our part of the world. Organic manure although considered having low nutrient content, on a prolonged use are cheap relatively, environment friendly and has proved to have positive benefits (Shaheen *et al.*, 2017). Organic manure improves soil physical and chemical property, soil structure, water holding capacity, increases organic matter and hence microbial count of soil (Dada and Ewulo, 2011). The presence of high population of microorganism, bacteria and fungi in organic manure, increases microbiological activities and results in higher mineralization of plant nutrients and hence increases nutrients availability in plant (Shrestha, 2008).

Studies by Dada (2011) indicate rapid multiplication of soil microbe in application of lime with poultry manure. Similarly, the application of organic manure improves vegetative growth by enhancing role of organic N in cell division and expansion (Singh and Agarwal, 2001). Some organic manures like vermicompost release nutrients in plant-available form in and thus enhance productivity (Sharma and Garg, 2018). Organic manures also ramp up root growth, help in water and nutrient absorption due to the hormonal substances in the vermicompost with better nutrient retention (Canellas *et al.*, 2002; Theunissen *et al.*, 2010; Sinha *et al.*, 2010). Farmacyard manure has been recorded in enhancing growth productivity

and nitrogen and potassium content (Citak and Sonmez, 2009). One such example includes use of poultry manure as fertilizer which increased cauliflower head weight by 17% (Moyin-Jesu, 2015). This indicates increased yield from organic manure.

Organic manure even when applied, are not applied sufficiently or are not applied at a clear recommended dose due to the vagueness regarding the subject. This study was done to identify and evaluate effects of different organic sources of nutrient used conventionally at different doses on growth and yield of cauliflower. Identification of the organic fertilizers that fulfill the nutrient requirement of the crop could help serve as an alternative and eventually substitute the indiscriminate use of chemical fertilizers. This would also help eradicate the problem of timely unavailability, quality and shortage of chemical fertilizers advocating the use of locally available organic fertilizers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site and design

The experiment was carried out at Sushila Agriculture farm, Bhojpur-4, Dawan, Bhojpur from 22nd February, 2020 to 4th May, 2020. The experiment was conducted using randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 4 different organic nutrient sources as treatments and a control was placed where each treatment was replicated 4 times. The geographical location of the experimental site was situated at elevation of 1256 masl. Seedlings of Cauliflower variety 'white top' were transplanted in the field with 45*45 cm spacing. And the experimental plot was maintained at size 2*1.5m². Each plot had 4 row and 5 plants were maintained in each row. Total number of plants per plot was maintained at 20. Total experimental area was 15* 10 m = 150 m².

Treatment structure

The seed material of "White top", and other inputs were procured from the local market, and the farm itself. Nursery was prepared with 1m width and 1.5m length. Field was ploughed using local plough twice followed by planking after which the clods were broken and weeds and other unwanted plant stubbles, stone, weed, roots, and other particles were removed. Twenty plots were prepared according to the experimental design adopted. Fifteen centimeter raised plots were made for proper root development and drainage facilities. All the observations regarding several growth parameters viz plant height, no of leaves per plant, leaf length, canopy area, curd weight & biomass weight were recorded from five randomly selected sample plants from each plot for observation and data recording.

Table 1. Treatments used in the experiment

S.N	Treatments	Notation	Organic Manures applied	
			(kg/plot)	(Mt/ha)
1	Farm Yard Manure	T1	6	20
2	Poultry manure	T2	4	13.3
3	Vermicompost	T3	4	13.3
4	Mustard oil cake	T4	1.3	4.3
5	Control	T5	-	-

Details of layout

Name of crop:	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> L. var. <i>botrytis</i> .
Cultivar/ variety:	“White top”
No. of Replications:	4
No. of Treatment:	5
Total number of plots:	20
Plots size:	2m x 1.5 m (3.0 m ²)
Total plot area:	15 m × 10 m (150 m ²)
Row to row distance:	45 cm
Plant to plant distance	45 cm

Growth parameters

Plant height (cm)

Plant height (cm) was measured on randomly selected 5 plants from 2 standard rows of each plot and their mean was calculated. It was measured at its major growth stages i.e. from 30 days after transplanting and at 15 days of interval. Its average was calculated and computed in cm.

Number of leaves per plant

Number of green leaves per plant were counted from the same plants selected for observations of plant height. The number of leaves per plant was counted from 30 days of transplanting.

Canopy area (cm²)

Area covered by the plant was measured in cm².

Curd weight (g)

The weight of curd from each plant was obtained by using the weighing balance machine.

Biomass weight (g)

The total weight of plant was taken after uprooting whole plant and weighed in weighing balance.

Statistical analysis

The growth and yield parameters mentioned above were measured and recorded which was then transferred to Ms Excel Sheet for tabulation and analysis of the results of the experiment. The data were analyzed using GenStat for analysis of variance (ANOVA) and critical difference (LSD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth parameters

Plant height

Table no.2 represents effect of different nutrient sources on plant height. The highest plant height (41.35cm) was observed on treatment with 20mt/ha FYM on 60 DAT. Least growth was observed with control at 30.60 cm. Plant height with FYM was the only treatment significantly different to the growth with regards to control. Besides that, plant height on 60 DAT with poultry manure was at 36.35cm followed by mustard oil cake at 36.33cm and vermicompost (34.75cm). Similarly, there was no significant difference on plant height with poultry manure, vermicompost and mustard oil cake, on 30 DAT and 45 DAT. In contrast to this, plant height with FYM varied significantly in 30 DAT and 45 DAT. Particularly, the reason for improved growth with FYM might be due to increased soil physical properties i.e. soil porosity, water holding capacity and supply of other plant growth promoting substances.

Table 2. Effect of different organic manure on plant height during different period of cauliflower growth at Bhojpur, 2020

Treatment	Plant height (cm)		
	30DAT	45DAT	60DAT
FYM	23.70 ^a	35.48 ^a	41.35 ^a
Poultry manure	15.10 ^b	26.95 ^b	36.35 ^b
Vermicompost	16.20 ^b	27.65 ^b	34.75 ^{bc}
Mustard oil cake	15.05 ^b	26.32 ^b	36.33 ^b
Control	12.85 ^b	21.95 ^b	30.60 ^c
Grand mean	16.58	27.67	35.88
SEM(\pm)	1.279	1.275	0.955
LSD	3.940	3.927	2.941
CV (%)	15.4	9.2	5.3

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure).

Number of leaves per plant

In case of number of leaves per plant, highest number per plant (17.57) was observed on FYM which was significantly different to that of control (13.20) on 60 DAT. The number of leaves per plant on vermicompost and poultry manure were similar at 15.75 for the former and 15.35 on the latter and both of them were varied significantly to the growth with control. The effects of organic manures on number of leaves/plants were significantly superior to control.

Table 3. Effect of different organic manure on number of leaves during different period of cauliflower growth at Bhojpur, 2020.

Treatment	Number of leaves		
	30DAT	45DAT	60DAT
FYM	7.750 ^a	11.425 ^a	17.57 ^a
Poultry manure	7.200 ^{ab}	9.650 ^b	15.35 ^{ab}
Vermicompost	7.375 ^{ab}	10.200 ^b	15.75 ^{ab}
Mustard oil cake	6.375 ^b	9.275 ^b	16.35 ^b
Control	6.125 ^b	8.125 ^c	13.20 ^b
Grand mean	6.96	9.735	15.64
SEM(±)	0.273	0.2035	0.637
LSD	0.842	0.6269	1.963
CV (%)	7.8	4.2	8.1

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure)

Leaf length

Most significant growth in leaf length was recorded in FYM at 35.05cm on 60 DAT followed by poultry manure (31.25cm), mustard oil cake (31.19cm) and vermicompost(29.83). the least leaf length measurement was observed with control (25.67cm). The leaf length with treatments varied significantly to that with control on 45 DAT and 60 DAT. Leaf elongation rate (LER) depends on Nitrogen supply which explains the growth and increase in leaf length from manure application. Yoshida et al. (1969) reported leaf length increased remarkably with additional supply of nitrogen. These result are in line with the findings of Ahmed Baloch *et al.* (2014)who found significant increase in number of leaves of radish with the sole application of NPK.

Table 4. Effect of different organic manure on leaf length during different period of cauliflower growth at Bhojpur, 2020.

Treatment	Leaf length (cm)		
	30DAT	45DAT	60DAT
FYM	20.52 ^a	27.78 ^a	35.05 ^a
Poultry manure	16.97 ^{ab}	21.68 ^{ab}	31.25 ^b
Vermicompost	16.10 ^{ab}	20.75 ^b	29.93 ^b
Mustard oil cake	16.52 ^{ab}	21.25 ^b	31.19 ^b
Control	12.30 ^b	13.95 ^c	25.67 ^c
Grand mean	16.48	21.08	30.62
SEM(±)	1.332	1.322	0.777
LSD	4.104	4.075	2.393
CV (%)	16.2	12.5	5.1

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure)

Canopy area

FYM significantly influenced canopy area and maximum canopy area (28.69cm) was recorded on 60 DAT. On 60 DAT, all treatments showcased significant difference in canopy area where spread of 24.50 cm in poultry manure, 22.33 cm in vermicompost and 22.15cm in mustard oil cake was observed.

Table 5. Effect of different organic manure on canopy area during different period of cauliflower growth at Bhojpur, 2020

Treatment	Canopy area (cm)		
	30DAT	45DAT	60DAT
FYM	12.500 ^a	22.75 ^a	28.69 ^a
Poultry manure	9.425 ^{ab}	20.05 ^{ab}	24.50 ^b
Vermicompost	9.050 ^{ab}	18.32 ^b	22.33 ^{bc}
Mustard oil cake	9.525 ^{ab}	18.63 ^{ab}	22.15 ^{bc}
Control	8.900 ^b	16.47 ^b	20.35 ^c
Grand mean	9.88	19.25	23.60
SEM (±)	1.157	0.879	0.576
LSD	3.564	2.709	1.775
CV (%)	23.4	9.1	4.9

Lowest canopy area was observed in control (20.35cm). Significant root growth after application of FYM might be due to proper root development, with increased availability of macro nutrients and micronutrients and hence flourishing canopy area. Similar study by Mojeremane, Chilume and Mathowa (2017) indicated growth in tomato canopy area with increased organic fertilizer application.

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure)

Curd weight

Concurring with other growth parameters, curd with maximum weight was produced on FYM plot. Highest curd yield (728.4gm) was observed in FYM and lowest curd yield (328.7gm) was observed in control. The curd yield recorded in all organic manure treatment was in general higher than control. Except for vermicompost (378.5gm), curd yield of all treatment; poultry manure (587.4gm), mustard oil cake (566gm) was significantly different to control. The promising results of FYM, vermicompost, poultry manure and mustard oil cake might be due to the higher content of readily available plant nutrients, organic matter, improved soil structure and easy root penetration and increased microbial biomass.

Table 6 Effect of different organic fertilizer sources on curd weight of cauliflower at Bhojpur, 2020

Treatment	Curd weight (g)
FYM	728.4 ^a
Poultry manure	587.4 ^b
Vermicompost	378.5 ^c
Mustard oil cake	566.0 ^b
Control	328.7 ^c
Grand mean	518
SEM (±)	27.7
LSD	85.3
CV (%)	10.7

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure).

Biomass weight

In case of biomass weight, all of the plants in treated plots varied significantly higher in weight to that of control. Highest biomass weight (1052g) was recorded in FYM, followed by vermicompost (1285g), poultry manure (1151g) and mustard oil cake (1018g) in that particular order. The lowest biomass weight (686g) was recorded in control. Higher biomass weight in all treated plots indicate improved overall growth in plots with organic manure due to increased, microbial activity, mineralization, soil organic matter and readily available plant nutrient.

Table 7. Effect of different organic nitrogen sources on Biomass weight of cauliflower at Bhojpur, 2020

Treatment	Biomass weight(gm)
FYM	1052 ^a
Poultry manure	1151 ^a
Vermicompost	1285 ^a
Mustard oil cake	1018 ^a
Control	686 ^b
Grand mean	1038
SEM(±)	61.7
LSD	190.2
CV (%)	11.9

Mean separated by DMRT and columns represented with the same letter (s) are non-significant at 5 % level of significance. Note: CV represent coefficient of variation, and LSD means least significance differences, NS (Non-significant), DAT (Days After Transplanting), FYM (Farm Yard Manure).

CONCLUSION

The study projected that application of organic manures resulted in significant improvement in all of the growth parameters and yield attributing factors of cauliflower. Out of all, FYM performed best in most growth parameters viz. plant height, number of leaves, leaf length canopy area and resulted in maximum yield while maximum biomass weight was observed on vermicompost. This study concludes that the performance of the cauliflower (white top) was better in FYM in comparison with other organic manures from both growth and yield parameters. Therefore this study considers FYM as the best alternative, along with other organic manures for increasing growth and productivity of the cauliflower keeping soil health in consideration.

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